

FORMATION OF TERMS USING IZOFA

Mahkamova Durdona Nematovna,

Senior Lecturer at Tashkent State University of

Uzbek Language and Literature,

durdonamahkamova7@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The article discusses the formation of terms using isofet. Types of isofa and terminological examples from terminological systems of the Uzbek language are given. An analysis of this case will be introduced.

Keywords: *terminology, Uzbek terminology, izofa, isophasic compound, terminological systems, adverbial suffix, medicine, physics, algebra.*

It is known that in Turkic languages, in particular, in Uzbek, words of the noun + noun type are combined by izofa [2,34]. Three types of izofa are distinguished: in the 1st type of izofa, both components are completely without grammatical form, that is, the relationship of such words is determined by word order and unifying intonation: *ochiq dengiz, ishchi dastur, intellektual mulk, etc.*

In the 2nd isophasic compound, the first component comes in the form of the main agreement, and the second component comes with a possessive suffix. For example: *seleksiya yutug'i, birja savdosi, birja bitimi, yer huquqi*, etc.

In type 3 izofa, the first component comes in the form of a nominative case, and the second component comes with a possessive suffix. It is in terms of this type that the grammatical indicator belonging to the first component can be used without a sign and a contraction phenomenon can occur.[1,86][7]

Type 1 determining compounds are a more convenient, compact and terminological form. According to the famous terminologist R. Doniyorov, this kind

of terms are clearly visible at first glance due to their terminological nature.[8] They acquire terminological meaning according to their content: because the first part of it can be adjectivized (adjectived), by which an adjectivized compound is formed in practice: *oyoq ulov, chiroq poya, gilbo 'ta g 'isht, shamol parrak, aravamix qolip*. This type of isophatic compounds is very ancient. When a certain concept cannot be expressed in words, the method of realizing it by means of a combination is very useful, especially in terminological systems. In particular, in the technical terminology of the Uzbek language, when it is not possible to make a relative quality from one or another word, the 1st type is characterized by the fact that it is convenient in every way.

The characteristic features of this type of izofa are presented in many scientific literature. A number of features such as its historicity, ease of compounding, full compatibility with language capabilities are listed and explained. The well-known linguist N.A. Baskakov also noted that the tendency to contraction in the morphological construction of Turkic languages is manifested in the presence of grammatical indicators (head agreement) called "zero form" in them. For us, the role of this formation in the formation of compact terms is important.[3, 28] In fact, this is the primary requirement of frugality. The term should be concise, short and, as far as possible, without additions and explanatory indicators. Only in this case, its formal aspect is exactly compatible with other lexical units.

Type 1 izofa is considered an ancient creation, so terms created by this method can be found in the terminology of fields with a long historical origin. For example, in medicine: *oshqozon, oyoqpanja, qontomir, qorinparda, qo 'lpanja, oziq tish, to 'qma parda, ichaktutqich*.

As mentioned, the possibility of the Uzbek language has its historical roots. However, the passage of time and the popularization of the term can also lead to the terms made by other methods in the form of type 1 izofa: *sharnirli mufta –sharnir mufta, po 'kakli qistirma-po 'kak qistirma, po 'latli lenta-po 'lat lenta* , etc.

Type 2 superlative combination is used in Turkic languages in cases where an object, thing, or event is related to a second object, thing, or event. In this type of izofa,

the first component is in indefinite agreement, and the second component takes a relative affix that means ownership (relationship). Such making has the form ot+ot+i(-si), and the presence of indefinite agreement in the form 0 indicates that the terms specific to this construction are also the object of our research.

In the technique: *havo filtri, moy nasosi, elektr tarmog'i, elektr ta'minoti*

In medicine: *taqim muskuli, lunj mushagi, peshona suyagi, so'lak bezlari, me'da og'zi, umurtqa pog'onasi*

In physics: *yadro izomeriyasi, yadro fotoeffekti, yadro energiyasi*

In jurisprudence: *fuqarolik jamiyati, fuqarolik ishi, jinoyat ishi, mulk huquqi, kafolat vekseli, yosh senzi*

According to linguists, type 2 isopha is very common and has three times more variants than type 3 isopha. According to the classifications, this type of izofa is divided into 21 options from the point of view of ownership. Of these variants, variant 12 exactly matches the word-formation patterns, in which the izofa is used to denote the object-to-subject relation: Chinese (Chinese dictionary).[4]

Professor H. Dadaboev explains [5][7] the specific aspects of this type of izofa on the example of its usage in "Devonu lug'otit turk" work, turning into a type with one affix, i.e. the first component without a demonstrative (genitive) affix, and the second component with a relative affix, i.e. turning into a type with a sign of both components of the phrase or noting that the property of non-reversibility is considered, he notes that most of the one-affix isotypes can easily become two-affix possessive isotypes, while some relative isotype variants did not transfer to the A1+B1 (type 3) affix variant. [7]This situation is typical for today's terminology. The reason is that in the formation of terms, the terms of type 2 izofal are completely different from the terms of izofal of type 3, and in almost no place it is noticed that the second type of izofal has become the third type or that it is used in a parallel way. Even if the third type is artificially moved to isomorphism, the semantics of the term will change and may cause confusion in the meaning of the term.[6]

Comparison:

Fuqarolik jamiyati(2-tip izofa) –fuqarolikning jamiyati(3-tip izofa), Fuqarolik ishi(2-tip izofa) –fuqarolikning ishi(3-tip izofa),Jinoyat ishi(2-tip izofa) –jinoyatning ishi(3-tip izofa)

The 3rd type of idiom, which is considered "real idiom", expresses the relation of the referential subject, in which the first component of the term brings the adverbial suffix, and the second component brings the possessive suffix. However, in most cases, for the sake of brevity, the grammatical indicator of the first component is used without a sign.

In medicine: *til ildizi (tilning ildizi), yurak qorinchasi (yurakning qorinchasi), halqum devori (halqumning devori), til tasmasi (tilning tasmasi);*

In physics: *energiya saqlanishi (energiyaning saqlanishi), tovush tezligi (tovushning tezligi), havo bosimi (havoning bosimi), massa zichligi (massaning zichligi);*

In jurisprudence: *davlat hududi (davlatning hududi), xolislari sudi (xolislarning sudi), yuk yig‘imi(yukning yig‘imi), advokat siri(advokatning siri).*

As can be seen, the elements of morphological contraction are more clearly visible in the third type of isotype. This type of izofa is considered to be one of the most effective ways of forming terms in terminology, and it is considered to be both semantically clear and compact in terms of form. In the compactification of multi-component terms, in most cases, the use of this type of addition gives good results.

Morphological economy can also be found in terms based on the relative adjective + noun pattern. In this case, the adjective formative suffix is shortened and thus a new term is formed. There may also be a change in the base mold. That is, the base that remains after the formative is reduced may not belong to a quality, but to another category.[9]

It has been confirmed that the *-simon* affix, which is defined as a passive formative in some literature on linguistics, is quite active in terminological research. There are specific reasons for the popularity of this affix, of course. It is known that in

languages, including the Uzbek literary language, making compounds based on the principle of similarity is one of the important methods that have been developed since ancient times. In order to realize this, in addition to the words *kabi*, *singari*, *o'xshash*, in the form of *-day*, *-dek*, *-namo*, etc., were also used. *-simon* affix is one of them. The fact that a suffix takes the place of a lexeme and takes the semantics of a lexeme and participates in the formation of a word (*nay shaklidagi suyak-naysimon suyak*) first of all indicates that the suffix serves economy.[9] As a result of the development of the compound terms made with the suffix *-simon*, such terms become compound words, and the suffix *-simon* is shortened. As a result, the morphological economy is revealed: *xalqa muskul* (*xalqasimon muskul*), *shohtog'ay* (*shohsimon tog'ay*), *no'xat suyak* (*no'xatsimon suyak*), *ayri bez* (*ayrisimon bez*)

The suffix *-li* is one of the most active additions[10] in the formation of compound terms, and the words related to the noun group to which this affix is added in the compound terms have meanings such as "possession", "existence". Even in compound terms, whose determining component is originally formed with this affix, the affix is shortened in many places as a result of the expansion and popularization of the term's use since the time when the term appeared:

in medicine: *mushakli vena- mushak vena*, *sig'imli tomir –sig'im tomir*, *do'ngli bo'g'im- do'ng bo'g'im*, *chekakli toshma-chekak toshma*;

in algebra: *qiymatli ifoda –qiymat ifoda*, *natijali xulosa-natija xulosa*.

In conclusion, it can be noted that morphological formation is more common in terminology compared to other types of word formation. At the same time, it is prone to change. The form of the created word can change, develop, or shorten based on the modernization of time and industry. However, this does not mean that the way of making the term changes. It is only considered as a formal change.

REFERENCES

1. Dadaboyev H. [O‘zbek terminologiyasi](#). –Toshkent, 2009
2. Dadaboyev H, Hamidov Z, Holmonova Z . [The history of the lexicology of the Uzbek Literary. Tashkent](#)
3. Dadaboyev H. [O‘zbek harbiy terminologiyasi](#). –Toshkent, 2021
4. Dadaboyev H. [Formation of diplomatic relations between timurid dynasty and chinese empire](#). ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 11 (6), 644-649
5. Dadaboyev H. [XI-XII. Yüzyıllar Eski Türk Dili Söz Varlığının Divânu Lugâti’t-Türk’teki İfadesi](#). // Bilig, 2022, P 97-118
6. Dadaboyev H. [Лексико-генетическая характеристика узбекской терминологии](#). //Til, ta’lim,tarjima xalqaro turkalogiya, 2020
7. Дадабоев Х. Бир аффиксли релятив изофа(A_0+B_1) нинг “Девону луғотит турк” асарида қўлланилиши.//Ўзбек тилшунослигининг долзарб муаммолари. – Андижон, 2012.
8. Дониёров Р.Ўзбек тили техник терминологиясининг айрим масалалари. – Тошкент: Фан, 1977. 101-бет
9. Майзель.С. Изафет в турецком языке. –М, -Л. 1957. с.31
10. Mahkamova D. [THE ROLE OF DJADIDS’ IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF UZBEK TERMINOLOGY](#).BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, 3(6), 1249–1252. 3 (6), 1249–1252.
11. Mahkamova D. Terminologik tizimda leksik modernizatsiyalashuvning voqelanishi. // O‘zbekiston: til va madaniyat. Lingvistika. 2022